

A STUDY ON LOCAL AND INTERNATIONAL FACTORS INFLUENCING THE PRODUCTION AND EXPORT OF COFFEE FROM KARNATAKA STATE

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ABSTRACT

India's coffee exports have grown significantly due to the increasing global demand for its rich and unique flavors. In the first half of January 2025, India exported over 9,300 tonnes of coffee, with top buyers including Italy, Belgium, and Russia. The main objective of this research is to study the local and international factors influencing the production and export of coffee from Karnataka state. Under the stratified sampling technique, from each district, one coffee-growing village was selected randomly for further sampling. A list of coffee growers from each village and a total of 312 farmers, including export traders, was prepared for the study purpose. For the analysis purpose, regression was used to find out the influence of local and international factors influencing the production and export of coffee from Karnataka. The research revealed that the international factors such as export incentives and logistical support, high product quality, adherence to international labelling and packaging standards, GDP of the destination, distance of the client country, foreign exchange, growing demand for value-added products like roasted and instant coffee, immense export expertise and knowledge, and coffee market liberalization were found significant with export satisfaction by the coffee exports from Karnataka state. It is also found that the unique contribution for the variables such as investment viability of coffee plantations, lesser production costs, higher yields, ecologically rich Western and Eastern Ghats, sustainability of coffee farming, setting up coffee processing plants, empowering farmers, small-scale producers together, and linking to the export market were influencing production and export satisfaction with the export of coffee by the coffee growers.

Keywords: Local, International, Influence, Coffee, Export, Karnataka

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1. INTRODUCTION

Coffee is a brewed drink prepared from roasted coffee beans, the seeds of berries from certain coffee species. The seed is separated from the fruit to produce green coffee. Green coffee is then roasted, which transforms the raw green coffee into a consumable product, roasted coffee. Roasted coffee is then ground into a powder and mixed with water to produce a cup of coffee (Das, A., 2020). Coffee is darkly colored, bitter, and slightly acidic and has a stimulating effect, primarily due to its caffeine content. Coffee plays a vital role in the Indian economy, serving as a significant agricultural export and a major source of income for millions of farmers, particularly in the southern states (Kodigehalli, B. V. 2011).

The coffee industry not only contributes to India's foreign exchange earnings but also supports rural development and employment in various regions of the country. Coffee occupies a place of pride among plantation crops grown in India. It is the most important cash crop that is grown in the tropics (Jagadeesh M. S., et al., 2024). Generally, coffee is the second largest traded commodity next to petroleum products. India's coffee was considered the best coffee in the world. To increase the sustainability of coffee production, an emphasis should be placed on improving coffee quality through sustainable, environmentally friendly cultivation practices, which can result in higher net returns in the long run (Shreedevi, B. C., et al., 2016).

India is becoming known around the world as one of the world's leading coffee producers. India produces some of the world's best coffee, which is grown in the shade. With over 3 million coffee growers, coffee cultivation is a source of employment in India. The coffee plant is a woody perennial evergreen dicotyledonous plant that belongs to the Rubiaceae family (Thanuja, P., and Singh, N. K., 2017). Two main species of coffee are cultivated today. *Coffea arabica*, known as Arabica coffee, accounts for 75-80 percent of the world's production. *Coffea canephora*, known as Robusta coffee, accounts for about 20 percent and differs from the Arabica coffees in terms of taste. History of coffee usage goes back to the thirteenth century (Arun, S. 2025). The Arabs were the first to cultivate and also to trade coffee. Coffee, nicknamed "Islamic milk" and "sage's milk," has conquered the third most popular drink after water and wine. Over 125 coffee-consuming countries, about 50 percent of them produce coffee. With 33.16 percent of the world's total coffee production, Brazil stands first, and with 4.5 percent of total coffee production, India stands seventh among the top coffee-producing countries (International Coffee Organization) (Balakrishnan, M. 2018). With the tune of 4000 crore Rs. of foreign exchange, Indian coffee has created itself a niche in the international market. In India, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, and Kerala are the three states cultivating the coffee predominantly. Karnataka, accounting for 71.03 percent of India's total coffee production, owns the pride place (Deepika, M., & Amalendu, J. 2013).

2. INDIA'S COFFEE EXPORT

India is primarily an export market for coffee, although demand for coffee in India is increasing. Cafes in urban areas, the gradual shift from the tea-drinking habit, and the preference of the millennials and Gen Z with changing lifestyles and values have continued to impact coffee consumption in India (Deepika, M.G. 2017). The primary coffee-growing regions of India are Karnataka, Kerala, and Tamil Nadu, forming the traditional coffee-growing region of the south, followed by the new areas developed in the nontraditional areas of Andhra Pradesh and Orissa on the eastern coast of the country, and with a third region comprising the states of Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Tripura, Nagaland, and Arunachal Pradesh in northeastern India (Gurusamy, P., & Yamakanith, P. 2015).

Table 1: States wise Support India's Coffee Industry

Rank	State	Key Facts	Production (2022-23, Tonnes)
1	Karnataka	Largest coffee producer in India; contributes around 70% of total output. Karnataka remains on top due to tradition, climate, and skill	248,000
2	Kerala	Known for smallholder Robusta farms in Wayanad and Idukki.	72,500
3	Tamil Nadu	Grows Arabica in hilly zones like Nilgiris and Shevaroyes.	18,700
4	Andhra Pradesh	Home to Araku Valley, where tribal farmers grow organic coffee.	12,260
5	Odisha	Coffee farms in hilly areas like Koraput are gaining attention.	465

(JASREET KAUR: 2025)

To enhance coffee production and meet growing domestic and international demand, the Coffee Board of India has launched several important initiatives (Kumareswaran, T., Singh, H., 2019). Through the Integrated Coffee Development Project (ICDP), the focus is on improving yields, expanding cultivation in non-traditional regions, and ensuring the sustainability of coffee farming. These measures are part of a comprehensive strategy to strengthen India's coffee industry, increase productivity, and improve its global competitiveness (Laxmiputra, 2022).

About seventy percent of coffee produced in India is exported to different countries around the world. India accounts for 3.26 percent of the world's coffee production and 3.02 percent of the world's coffee export and ranks seventh and fifth in coffee production and export, respectively (Sreereshma S R et al., 2025). Italy, the Russian Federation, Germany, Poland, Belgium, and Spain are the major export destinations for Indian coffee (Madappa, C. D., & Hosamane, M. D. 2011).

Table 2: Exports of Coffee from India by Countries - FY 2015/16 - 2023/2024

(Green Bean Equivalent - Quantity in MT)

Destination	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	2023-24*
ITALY	77361	83560	79024	76452	63605	59002	75502	58276	19619
GERMANY	28286	34804	39128	31818	34099	32205	37949	42792	14781
RUSSIAN FEDERATION	25306	28805	26345	22293	26862	16179	24802	38664	10506
BELGIUM	15909	19994	18106	18510	19941	23856	29495	27096	9456
TURKEY	15180	17230	15951	14742	10723	6029	15497	19431	6875
POLAND	6493	11133	13709	14056	16503	11749	12790	16126	5147
LIBYA	6019	6447	10545	10301	3811	9790	10722	11840	2853
INDONESIA	2957	5241	12152	10113	5060	2636	2738	5515	
MALAYSIA	5788	6389	6918	9201	7735	8588	8317	10983	3099
JORDAN	9407	6972	10778	9095	7604	9197	17837	14087	5806
SPAIN	6295	9593	9960	7663	7155	5330	6619	5072	2418
U.S.A.	5418	7361	13398	7354	7037	8072	10422	10081	3690
UKRAINE	3844	5096	6748	7327	6947	5711	6880	1926	1644
SLOVENIA	10910	10059	8985	6687	5525	4155	4589	5295	1264
AUSTRALIA	6759	5599	7857	6398	5985	6168	6808	5869	2370
GREECE	6533	7790	5616	6137	5607	5503	7725	6527	2559
KUWAIT	5343	5001	6457	5870	6675	6647	6032	6364	2636
KOREA,REPUBLIC OF-S	2279	4513	4273	4618	4034	4269	4828	5563	2292
SYRIA	1634	4028	3149	4482	3366	2054	5900	3735	1609
ISRAEL	4064	3317	5199	4356	4347	4780	7203	6438	1102
SAUDI ARABIA	3688	3511	4846	4293	3152	3793	5352	6341	1563
UNITED KINGDOM	2592	3046	3113	3849	4427	3388	4300	5945	3054
IRAN,ISLAMIC R/O	886	866	2056	3830	4181	3253	2450	2532	881
CROATIA	529	1768	2381	3709	3869	3573	4600	3355	1686
PORTUGAL	3359	3786	3659	3533	3006	2441	2280	1541	1887
VIETNAM	995	912	3035	3449	2915	1356	4246	3896	1027
FRANCE	3573	2713	3372	3319	2307	1572	1627	2452	947
UA EMIRATES	1911	2289	2406	3142	2753	4662	9316	17476	6132
EGYPT	1649	1334	2682	3022	3477	3764	7000	4345	1187
SWITZERLAND	2807	2248	2245	2917	3312	4978	2815	2969	1223
NETHERLANDS	1209	2459	2987	2653	2740	3065	2880	2418	2332
FINLAND	4038	3125	2268	2357	1248	383	634	981	857
TAIWAN	2780	2911	3031	2320	2489	3134	2427	2800	828
SINGAPORE	1419	1475	1613	1737	1705	1645	1389	573	118
SENEGAL	1020	1598	1610	1586	1281	1404	1533	1156	734
BENIN	545	1276	1426	1570	1757	2838	2294	923	69
MOROCCO	563	783	2134	1505	1791	1368	2871	1078	257
MONTENEGRO	1610	1406	1483	1481	653	1122	1783	1517	472
BANGLADESH	311	782	1157	1465	1656	1835	2455	2957	780
CANADA	1044	1179	1176	1407	1175	672	931	1125	207
ALBANIA	1001	1459	768	1348	1832	1317	1425	1410	727
MALI	1870	1766	1748	1238	1711	3100	1179	389	132
ROMANIA	1589	1771	1096	1140	683	674	1227	1279	310
SULTANATE OF OMAN	841	960	1206	1063	725	594	341	44	29
TOGO	561	935	1099	995	761	1216	1448	1032	275
NIGERIA	856	680	1029	970	1185	2510	1993	898	445
JAPAN	1323	836	715	926	777	1148	1130	907	316
LATVIA	925	831	732	899	971	1126	1215	806	370
IVORY COAST	394	728	84	844	558	601	1054	101	
DENMARK	872	1422	1485	841	713	67	3	3	
MAURITANIA	542	799	788	776	700	1144	1929	237	264
LITHUANIA	298	361	453	708	237	71	130	77	
LEBANON	158	287	513	706	272	402	1519	2710	1182
NEW ZEALAND	280	354	401	664	425	374	479	458	139

CHINA,PEOPLE'S R/O	476	590	522	636	770	729	779	430	243
BURKINA FASO	1061	1092	1049	629	837	801	325	152	47
NIGER	1603	1191	1252	590	323	545	1367	952	1054
NEPAL	255	428	429	565	763	765	1073	1178	364
OTHERS	12984	14059	23446	7422	9800	11297	29487	15221	6289
TOTAL	310204	352945	391796	353576	326554	310647	413942	396346	138153

* FY - Financial year (April to March). Includes re-exports, *based on export permits upto 31.07.2023
 (Source: <https://coffeeboard.gov.in/Database>)

Table 3: India's Coffee Exports during 2000-01 to 2023-24

Year	Coffee Exports (Rs. In Crores)	Annual Growth Rate	Share in Total Agriculture Exports	Share in Total Exports
2000-01	1185	-----	4.14	0.57
2001-02	1095	-7.59	3.68	0.51
2002-03	994	-9.22	2.86	0.38
2003-04	1086	9.26	2.91	0.36
2004-05	1069	-1.57	2.56	0.28
2005-06	1731	61.93	3.51	0.37
2006-07	1969	13.75	3.15	0.34
2007-08	1872	-4.93	2.36	0.28
2008-09	2256	20.51	2.62	0.26
2009-10	2032	-9.93	2.27	0.24
2010-11	3010	48.13	2.50	0.26
2011-12	4535	50.66	2.42	0.31
2012-13	4711	3.88	2.04	0.28
2013-14	4799	1.87	1.85	0.25
2014-15	4973	3.63	2.12	0.26
2015-16	5125	3.06	2.37	0.29
2016-17	5669	10.61	2.49	0.30
2017-18	6245	10.16	2.51	0.31
2018-19	5722	-8.37	2.11	0.24
2019-20	5237	-8.48	2.11	0.23
2020-21	5340	1.97	1.73	0.24
2021-22	7614	42.58	2.03	0.24
2022-23	9191	20.71	2.14	0.25
2023-24	10645	15.82	2.60	0.29

Source: Indiastat.

Table 3 portrays the value of coffee exports, which has decreased from Rs.1185 crores in 2000-01 to Rs.1086 crores in 2003-04, and also its share in total agriculture exports, which has dwindled from 4.15 percent to 3 percent during the corresponding years. Then this value drastically accelerated from Rs.1069 crores in 2004-05 to Rs.1731 crores in 2005-06. The value has slightly decreased from Rs.1969 crores in 2006-07 to Rs.1872 crores in 2007-08 due to a rise in freight rates to European countries. The value of coffee exports has decreased from Rs.2256 crores in 2008-09 to Rs.2032 crores in 2009-10 due to the low price of coffee in the world market. The coffee export has significantly increased from Rs.4535 crores in 2011-12 to Rs.4799 in 2013-14, but its share in total agriculture exports has plummeted from 2.52 percent to 1.84 percent during corresponding years. The coffee export has accelerated from Rs.5125 crores in the year 2015-16 to the level of Rs.5669 crores in 2016-17. After that, coffee export has slightly decreased from Rs.6245 crores in 2017-18 to Rs.5722 crores in 2018-19 due to a plummet in shipment of robusta and instant coffee varieties. The value has tremendously increased from Rs.5340 crores in 2020-

21 to Rs.7614 crores in 2021-22 due to increased demand from European buyers stockpiling ahead of the European Union's new Deforestation Regulation (EUDR). Then this value significantly accelerated from Rs.9191 crores in 2022-23 to Rs.10645 crores in 2023-24 due to increasing global demand for its rich and unique flavors and top buyers including Italy, Belgium, and Russia. India's export value of coffee has registered negative growth. During the years 2001-02, 2002-03, 2007-08, 2018-19, and 2019-2020, the coffee exports have registered negative growth. In the year 2005-06 the annual growth of coffee exports registered the highest level of 61.93 percent, and in the year 2013-14 the growth registered the lowest level of 1.87 percent. In the year 2000-01 the share of total agriculture exports of coffee exports registered the highest level of 4.14 percent, and in the year 2020-21 the share registered the lowest level of 1.73 percent. In the year 2000-01, the shares in total exports of coffee exports registered the highest level of 0.57 percent, and in the year 2019-20, the share registered the lowest level of 0.23 percent.

3. COFFEE PRODUCTION IN KARNATAKA

India's coffee production and export data, coupled with the analysis of trade potential, illustrate both strengths and areas for improvement in its export strategy. India stands as a significant player in the global coffee market, producing a substantial volume of coffee, particularly in the state of Karnataka. Karnataka is the highest producer of coffee in the country (Amaravathi and Raja A. S., 2014). Karnataka is able to produce coffee beans that are exported throughout the world. Karnataka leads in production due to its growing conditions, which include hilly areas with a cool climate and enough rainfall. Karnataka is located in southern India and has the ecological land of the Western Ghats, which is recognized by UNESCO as a world heritage site (Sushma K K, Perumunda, S 2025). The growing districts of Karnataka are the stagnant hills of Chikmagalur, Coorg (Kodagu), and Hassan, which have the right conditions of frequency of rainfall. He reasons for producing the highest coffee due to the following reasons (Padmanabha, 2016). Climate: Karnataka contains a unique set of growing conditions and climate pattern schemes that form the basis for coffee farming. Generally, Kerala has the misty mornings, moist environment, rainy monsoon climate, and relatively cool weather, which will foster the growth of high-quality Arabica and Robusta beans (Prakash, K. G., et al., 2022). Land Use: Coffee is mainly grown on hilly, shaded plantations in Karnataka, where farmers often grow pepper, cardamom, and other crops alongside coffee, adding value to the land. Types of Coffee: India grows two main types of coffee: the soft and aromatic Arabica and the robust Robusta. Coffee from Karnataka is exported as green beans or as part of blends of roasted and instant coffee to Italy, Germany, and Russia. Irrigation: Coffee naturally requires less water than rice, but Karnataka's year-round rainfall and abundant water conservation aids ensure that the water required for Karnataka's needs is limited primarily to the rainwater holding capacity of the soil. Tradition: Karnataka has a long historical narrative lined with cultural roots of coffee farming. The coffee story in India started with Baba Budan, who carted coffee beans into Chikmagalur. Since then, the people of Karnataka have developed artisanship around growing, harvesting, and processing coffee (Jagadeesh M. S., et al., 2024).

South Indian filter coffee has, over time, made a name internationally as well. Cultural Significance: Coffee is a culture in Karnataka, particularly in Coorg and Chikmagalur, where it is woven into the fabric of local identity. Each indigenous family has their own way of preparing coffee, and the tradition has circulated from generation to generation (Saroj, S. & Dr. Sanjay Saroj. 2019). Tourism and Coffee: Coffee estates in Karnataka provide opportunities for homestays and guided tours of coffee plantations. Visitors can see how coffee is cultivated, harvested, roasted, and brewed, thereby developing a relationship with both the coffee and tourism industry in Karnataka (Shalima Devi, G. M., Anil Kumar, K. S., 2009). Employment: Over 700,000 people are employed and dependent on the coffee industry in Karnataka in a variety of roles, including farmers, estate workers, sorters, transporters, and sellers. Coffee also supports small enterprises, including cafes and roasteries. Export: In 2023-24, India exported over USD \$1.29 billion worth of coffee, primarily from Karnataka (Rakash, K. G., et al., 2022).

Table 4: (Production in Karnataka) (in MT)

Sl. No.	State/District	2023-2024*			2022-2023		
		Arabica	Robusta	Total	Arabica	Robusta	Total
1	Chikkamagaluru	41,900	51,150	93,050	37,150	45,300	82,450
2	Kodagu	21,060	109,225	130,285	19,120	109,600	128,720
3	Hassan	19,000	24,550	43,550	15,750	21,100	36,850
	Total	81,960	184,925	266,885	72,020	176,000	248,020

(Source: <https://coffeeboard.gov.in/Database>)

The increase in overall coffee production from 2022-23 to 2023-24, particularly in both Arabica and Robusta varieties, showcases Karnataka's growing capacity to meet international demand.

4. LITERATURE REVIEW

The analysis reveals that India has the highest trade potential in the United Kingdom, France, the Netherlands, the United States, and Poland. However, India has already exhausted its trade potential in markets like Italy, Belgium, Jordan, Germany, and Slovenia (Soujanya, C. K., et al., 2023). Interestingly, India's major export destinations are primarily those where its trade potential is already exhausted. This paradox highlights the disconnect between India's trade potential and its current export focus, suggesting an opportunity to redirect efforts toward underutilized markets (Upendranadh, C. 2010). Countries with closer proximity to India are more likely to import Indian coffee, whereas distant markets, despite potential demand, face higher transportation costs, which dampens trade (Sunagar, M., & Arahunasi, U. H. 2022). This finding suggests a need for India to explore and invest in cost-effective logistics solutions to enhance its competitiveness in distant but lucrative markets. A critical insight from this study is the mismatch between India's actual export destinations and its untapped trade potential (Sunagar, M., & Arahunasi, U. H. 2022). The analysis reveals that while India has exhausted its trade potential in key markets like Italy, Belgium, and Germany, these countries remain major export destinations (Upendranadh, C. 2010). Conversely, markets with significant untapped potential, such as the United Kingdom, France, and the

Netherlands, are not fully leveraged (Soujanya, C. K., et al., 2023). This misalignment indicates an opportunity for India to diversify its export strategy by focusing on underutilized markets where its coffee could achieve greater market penetration (Das, A., 2020). To strengthen its position in the global coffee market, India must address both the internal and external factors influencing its export competitiveness (Kodigehalli, B. V. 2011). This includes improving production efficiency, enhancing product quality, and aligning export strategies with markets that offer the most significant growth potential (Rakash, K. G., et al., 2022). By redirecting efforts toward these underexploited markets and optimizing supply chain logistics, India can improve its competitiveness and secure a more robust and sustainable position in the global coffee trade (Jagadeesh M. S., et al., 2024). These initiatives, combined with export incentives and logistical support, are playing a crucial role in expanding India's coffee industry. They help improve both domestic production and global competitiveness, firmly establishing India as a leading player in the global coffee market (Shreedevi, B. C., et al., 2016). Indian coffee exports display a strong seasonal tilt, with exports peaking from March to June. Coffee is a highly seasonal product, and it is challenging to harvest, transport, and store it. All the steps from production to export require immense expertise and knowledge (Thanuja, P., and Singh, N. K., 2017). As a commodity, instant coffee enjoys the product feature of convenience—a quality in high demand and vital to today's global, fast-paced life. Since more than 50% of instant coffee is exported from Andhra Pradesh, many other states could attempt to mimic Andhra Pradesh by setting up coffee processing plants to boost India's overall coffee exports (Arun, S. 2025). Coffee cultivation in India assumes importance not only because it provides foreign exchange through exports but also from the perspective of the livelihoods of a large number of small growers and plantation workers (Balakrishnan, M. 2018). In the study (Deepika, M., & Amalendu, J. 2013), the export performance of coffee in India is observed to be acceptable, and it tends to be improved by increasing the value of the coffee beans at the beginning. Coffee is one of the well-known drinks on the planet (Deepika, M.G. 2017). Coffee utilization in India consistently expanded; sending out procurement acquired by exchanging coffee is agreeable at the present, and it is anticipated to be better in the future. In here, India has been a profound exporter of coffee to Italy from the top five nations (Gurusamy, P., & Yamakanith, P. 2015). On the off chance that administration steps up in supporting the coffee producers, the market will track down a superior possibility (Kumareswaran, T., Singh, H., 2019). Laxmiputra (2022), in their study, explain the production and export performance of coffee in India. The area, production, and export quantity of coffee registered a similar and fluctuating growth rate during the overall study of coffee area and production for strengthening the coffee exports in India. This ought to be finished by adopting new technology and cultivation practices for coffee-growing regions (Sreereshma S R et al., 2025). There is a fluctuation in the export performance of coffee due to the rising number of international exporters, but it is a constant and positive trend in the overall study period. If the government takes proper initiative in supporting the coffee producers, in addition to the exporters, the market will find constant prospects (Madappa, C. D., & Hosamane, M. D. 2011). The coffee supply chain works in an international

way; the direct link between producers and consumers is not present. Coffee is traded down a complex line of intermediaries, ranging from local traders, exporters, international traders, roasters, and retailers, who each capture a percentage of the retail value of coffee (Amaravathi and Raja A. S., 2014). In the Indian coffee industry there have been huge developments in the future markets for coffee. Despite the efforts to disseminate information, participation of smallholders in the future markets has been relatively low so far. However, it has helped in widening the access to markets, empowering farmers to make better cropping and selling decisions (Sushma K K, Perumunda, S 2025). Furthermore, it has facilitated the upgrading of storage, grading, and technology infrastructure. Indeed, there is a reduction in information asymmetries (Shalima Devi, G. M., Anil Kumar, K. S., 2009). In recent years, there has been a huge demand for certified and specialty coffee, including the traceability of the product in the chain. However, this requires meeting certain standards from the level of production (Padmanabha, 2016). Value addition to the green coffee involves the cost of certification, promotion of quality improvement, raising the reputation of the origin, good marketing skills, and also sometimes costly physical investments (Prakash, K. G., et al., 2022). This requires a certain level of good organizational development for producers to meet the legal, quality, and volume requirements of the international buyers (Jagadeesh M. S., et al., 2024). It is not possible to meet this huge demand from the international buyers by a single small-scale producer; hence, efforts should be made to bring the small-scale producers together and link them directly to the export market (Saroj, S. & Dr. Sanjay Saroj. 2019).

5. RESEARCH PROBLEM

Coffee is one of the world's most popular beverages; some claim it is the most widely consumed liquid in the world aside from water. Coffee's success as a beverage undoubtedly owes both to the caffeine it harbors and its sensory pleasure. Coffee lovers come to associate the energizing lift of the caffeine with the richness and aroma of the beverages that deliver it. Coffee is produced from the seeds of a small red fruit that grows halfway in size between a shrub and a tree. Coffee production is a labor-intensive process involving a vast intercontinental collaboration. The coffee market is oversupplied. Sixty to sixty-five percent of the world supply of coffee is from Latin America. Indian coffee has created a niche for itself in the international market, and the Indian coffees are earning a high premium, particularly Indian Robusta, which is highly preferred for its good blending quality. Arabica coffee from India is also well received in the international market. After intensive literature review, it is understood that there is a need for identifying and analyzing indicators of local and international factors affecting production and export of coffee from Karnataka State, which helps in developing conceptual theory and constructing an integrated model for enhancing export performance by the coffee farmers and traders. The main reason for conducting this research is to develop systematic knowledge to increase the performance in the field of production and export of coffee after considering international and local factors affecting the production and export of coffee from Karnataka.

6. NEED FOR THE STUDY

India exports 80 percent of its production. Indian coffee contributes only a meager share of about 5 percent in the global market. This global scene in the coffee industry entails a project study that reveals the various statistical details in areas like coffee production, coffee consumption, and export earnings, which further provides a vision that has to be achieved in the coffee industry in the forthcoming years. This study also reveals the influence of local and international factors on the production and export of coffee from Karnataka state. The industry is currently employing five million people and is anticipated to increase its export of opportunities in the near future. The export of coffee has been showing a constantly increasing trend right from its inception. The study on export performance of coffee, taking into consideration the major coffee-producing states, would bring out the importance of coffee exports. The study also identifies and analyzes the factors affecting the production and export of coffee from Karnataka State.

7. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Approximately three-fourths of India's coffee production consists of Arabica and Robusta beans. These are primarily exported as unroasted beans. However, there is a growing demand for value-added products like roasted and instant coffee, further fueling the export boom. This study area covers the Chikkamagaluru, Kodagu, and Hassan districts. The study indicators consist of international and local factors affecting the production and export of coffee from India.

8. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To examine the influence of international factors on the production and coffee export of coffee growers in the state of Karnataka.
2. To explore the influence of local factors on production and coffee export of coffee growers in the state of Karnataka.
3. To provide suitable suggestions and recommendations for the export of coffee from Karnataka State.

9. HYPOTHESIS

H1₀: There is no significant influence of international factors on the production and coffee export of coffee growers in the state of Karnataka.

H1: There is a significant influence of international factors on production and coffee export of coffee growers in the state of Karnataka.

H2₀: There is no significant influence of local factors on the production and coffee export of

coffee growers in the state of Karnataka.

H2: There is a significant influence of local factors on production and coffee export of coffee growers in the state of Karnataka.

10. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research uses descriptive analytical methods based on fieldwork, selected samples, and independent and dependent measurements. The hypotheses are developed to identify the significant relationship between the variables. The variables related to international and local factors were selected from a related literature review. The present research is descriptive and analytical in nature, which applies a regression model to understand the significant relationship of international and local factors with export satisfaction of farmers and export traders. Multiple regression analysis has been used to test the hypotheses framed. A structured questionnaire was developed to conduct a preliminary survey by selecting 10 firms on a random basis. Once the questionnaire achieved the reliability of the variables selected, the final survey was administered. Chikkamagaluru, Kodagu, and Hassan, districts having a predominant place in both the area of production and export of coffee in Karnataka state, were selected purposively. The appropriate sampling technique for selecting coffee growers and export traders for research in Karnataka State is stratified sampling. From each district, one coffee-growing village was selected randomly for further sampling. A list of coffee growers from each village, totalling 312 farmers, including export traders, was prepared for the study purpose.

11. DATA COLLECTION

i) Primary data

The first time data has been through a self-administered structured questionnaire, which was developed and asked to be filled out. Personal interviews were also done with respondents. A structured questionnaire was prepared containing These statements were rated on a five-point scale with scale agreements ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. "Strongly agree" was assigned a score of 5, "agree" a score of 4, "can't say" a score of 3, "disagree" a score of 2, and "strongly disagree" a score of 1 for conducting regression analysis.

ii) Secondary Data

The following are the sources from which the secondary data was collected, such as information that has been gathered from selected peer-reviewed articles from bibliographic databases (Emerald, Sage journals online, Science Direct, Scopus, Taylor & Francis online, Web of Science, and Wiley (online library). Peer-reviewed journals were considered based on their knowledge validity and their highest impact on the research field. Online E-Sources, Published reports, journals, theses, magazines, research articles, newspapers, etc.

12. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

International factors influencing the production and export coffee in Karnataka State

H1₀: There is no significant influence of international factors on the production and coffee

export of coffee growers in the state of Karnataka.H1: There is a significant influence of international factors on production and coffee export of coffee growers in the state of Karnataka. Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.777 ^a	.604	.588	.72767		
ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	241.525	12	20.127	38.012	.000 ^a
	Residual	158.321	299	.530		
	Total	399.846	311			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.877	.200		4.388	.000
	Export incentives and logistical support.	.744	.099	.736	7.515	.000
	High product quality.	.270	.088	.263	3.075	.002
	Competitive pricing.	.001	.081	.002	.016	.987
	Adherence to international labelling and packaging standards.	-.316	.073	-.379	-4.310	.000
	GDP of the destination	-.331	.089	-.348	-3.726	.000
	Distance of the client country	.376	.107	.368	3.514	.001
	Foreign exchange	-.238	.096	-.246	-2.484	.014
	Efforts toward capturing underexploited markets	.023	.073	.026	.321	.749
	Growing demand for value-added products like roasted and instant coffee	-.260	.070	-.277	-3.742	.000
	Institutional support (Coffee Board of India)	.104	.089	.092	1.168	.244
	Immense export expertise and knowledge	.262	.058	.263	4.523	.000
	Coffee market liberalization	.320	.055	.314	5.821	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Export Satisfaction

A multiple regression analysis was used to investigate the impact of 12 variables of international factors on coffee grower's expert Satisfaction. From the above table it is understood that, that international factors (R= .777) indicating high degree of correlation among the variables, t = 4.388, p < .01) had a positively significant effect on coffee grower's expert satisfaction. Hence, it can be concluded that if the average level of international factors were high, the average level of coffee grower's expert Satisfaction would also be high. The analysis also reveals that international factors were able to explain the total variation in coffee grower's expert Satisfaction by the regression model about R² 60.4% being high indicating model fits the data well. Thus answering the hypothesis H1: There is a significant influence of international factors on production and coffee export of coffee growers in the state of Karnataka., posited for this research is accepted. The coefficient table shows the contribution of each international factors on export satisfaction. From

the above table the beta values demonstrate the unique contribution for the variables such as Export incentives and logistical support. ($\beta = .744$) ($p = .000$), High product quality ($\beta = .270$) ($p = .002$), Adherence to international labelling and packaging standards ($\beta = -.316$) ($p = .000$), GDP of the destination ($\beta = -.331$) ($p = .000$), Distance of the client country ($\beta = .376$) ($p = .001$), Foreign exchange ($\beta = -.238$) ($p = .014$), Growing demand for value-added products like roasted and instant coffee ($\beta = -.260$) ($p = .000$), Immense export expertise and knowledge ($\beta = .262$) ($p = .000$) and Coffee market liberalization ($\beta = .320$) ($p = .000$) we're influencing production and export satisfaction with export of coffee by the coffee growers.

Local factors influencing the production and export coffee in Karnataka State

H2₀: There is no significant influence of local factors on the production and coffee export of coffee growers in the state of Karnataka.

H2: There is a significant influence of local factors on production and coffee export of coffee growers in the state of Karnataka.

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.575 ^a	.330	.303	1.03668		
ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	158.325	12	13.194	12.277	.000 ^a
	Residual	321.339	299	1.075		
	Total	479.663	311			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.100	.321		6.538	.000
	Investment viability of coffee plantation	.098	.051	.097	1.913	.057
	Maintenance cost of coffee plantation	.097	.056	.084	1.715	.087
	Lesser production costs	-.210	.060	-.206	-3.481	.001
	Higher yields	.839	.135	.761	6.194	.000
	Ecologically rich western and eastern Ghats.	.454	.127	.408	3.580	.000
	Sustainability of coffee farming	-.433	.118	-.467	-3.657	.000
	Monsoon rainfall conditions	-.027	.098	-.030	-.272	.786
	Setting up coffee processing plants	-.237	.107	-.234	-2.216	.027
	Livelihoods of large number of small growers and plantation workers	-.217	.140	-.196	-1.554	.121
	Adopting new technology and cultivation practices	.141	.122	.134	1.159	.247
	Empowering farmers.	.181	.091	.188	2.000	.046
	Small scale producers together and link to the export market	-.222	.086	-.216	-2.582	.010

a. Dependent Variable: Export Satisfaction

A multiple regression analysis was used to investigate the impact of 12 variables of local factors on coffee grower's expert Satisfaction. From the above table it is understood that, that local factors ($R = .575$) indicating high degree of correlation among the variables, $t = 6.538$, $p < .01$) had a

positively significant effect on coffee grower's expert Satisfaction. Hence, it can be concluded that if the average level of local factors were high, the average level of coffee grower's expert Satisfaction would also be high.

The analysis also reveals that local factors were able to explain the total variation in coffee grower's expert Satisfaction by the regression model about R^2 33% being high indicating model fits the data well. Thus answering the hypothesis H2: There is a significant influence of local factors on production and coffee export of coffee growers in the state of Karnataka, posited for this research is accepted. The coefficient table shows the contribution of each international factors on export satisfaction.

From the above table the beta values demonstrate the unique contribution for the variables such as Investment viability of coffee plantation ($\beta=.098$) ($p=.057$), Lesser production costs ($\beta=-.210$) ($p=.001$), Higher yields ($\beta=.839$) ($p=.000$), Ecologically rich western and eastern Ghats ($\beta=.454$) ($p=.000$), Sustainability of coffee farming ($\beta=-.433$) ($p=.000$), Setting up coffee processing plants ($\beta=-.237$) ($p=.027$), Empowering farmers ($\beta=.181$) ($p=.046$), Small scale producers together and link to the export market ($\beta=-.222$) ($p=.010$), we're influencing production and export satisfaction with export of coffee by the coffee growers.

13. RESEARCH FINDINGS

It is found that the international factors such as export incentives and logistical support, high product quality, adherence to international labelling and packaging standards, GDP of the destination, distance of the client country, foreign exchange, growing demand for value-added products like roasted and instant coffee, immense export expertise and knowledge, and coffee market liberalization were found significant with export satisfaction by the coffee exports from Karnataka state. It is also found that the unique contribution for the variables such as investment viability of coffee plantations, lesser production costs, higher yields, ecologically rich Western and Eastern Ghats, sustainability of coffee farming, setting up coffee processing plants, empowering farmers, small-scale producers together, and linking to the export market were influencing production and export satisfaction with the export of coffee by the coffee growers.

INTEGRATED RESEARCH MODEL

14. LIMITATIONS

1. The study took into account only international and local factors impacting the production and export of coffee from Karnataka state; there might be other factors impacting the export of coffee.
2. While there are other major coffee-growing regions in India that differ from this region in terms of agro-ecological patterns, varieties of coffee are cultivated and cultural practices are followed.
3. The study is carried out as a single student investigation with time and resources being the major constraints; it is limited to the Chikkamagaluru, Kodagu, and Hassan districts in Karnataka. Its results might not be entirely applicable to other coffee-growing areas in India or worldwide, where market conditions and agricultural techniques could vary.
4. Primary information obtained is mainly based on the interviews. Hence, there may be bias in the opinions given by the respondents. Thus, generalizations made based on the findings of the present study have limited application in the non-study area.
5. The study mostly offers cross-sectional data from certain moments in time; it lacks a long-term perspective on how price changes, climate change, or changing market dynamics influence profitability over several years.
6. Although the research addresses smallholders, the sample size and geographic distribution of smallholder farms might not completely reflect the variety of methods and difficulties experienced by all coffee producers, particularly those in rural or less accessible locations.
7. Although the paper addresses export business, it does not undertake a thorough examination of the present institutional environment or the viability of applying these policies on a broad scale, given bureaucratic, budgetary, and logistical issues.
8. The time factor is the major constraint of this study.

9. SUGGESTIONS

The trend in coffee export can be improved by improving the quality of coffee to international standards, and the export quantity of coffee can be increased by offering intentional competitive prices, and the process of packing should use airtight technology and aluminum packaging to preserve the aroma and taste as well as to avoid damage by light or heat. By reducing the cost per kilogram of green beans, Karnataka growers can offer more competitive export pricing. The Coffee Board already provides extension services such as soil sampling, pest control training, etc. Use the incentives provided by the Coffee Board, e.g., freight/transit assistance and machinery subsidies for roasting/grinding/packaging. Currently, Europe remains the top destination for Indian coffee. Karnataka should systematically target underutilized regions: e.g., Latin America (for blends), Africa (for niche origins), Southeast Asia (rising coffee consumption), and newer markets in Eastern Europe, CIS, Africa, and South & Southeast Asia. Develop market intelligence: The Coffee Board of India (CBI) already provides export-market information and global trends. Use embassies/trade missions, trade fairs, and buyer-seller meets to unlock these markets. Karnataka has strong origin branding potential (e.g., GI-tagged coffees such as Coorg Arabica). By offering specific origin-labelled coffees, microlots, traceability, sustainable shade-grown, etc., Karnataka exporters can command premiums, which helps pricing competitiveness (rather than competing on lowest cost only). The Coffee Board's proposed national certification for producers will help quality & export credibility. Many buyers pay for origin, story, and sustainability. The state and national effort should aim to reduce export turnaround time, improve port connectivity and container handling, and reduce wastage/moisture loss—enabling better pricing competitiveness. Use state-supported schemes (e.g., One District One Product in Kodagu) to support small enterprises around coffee. Growers/exporters should actively engage with CBI for training programs such as the “VIKRAYAM” incubation program. Encouragement for FPOs and small-grower collective engagement, particularly via CBI extension services. To compete globally (in export markets), exporters must ensure uniform quality (bean size, moisture content, defect rates), proper processing, storage, and packaging. Use CBI's services for moisture & outturn testing. Invest in traceability and certification (organic, shade-grown, and sustainability) so that international buyers see reliability—this can translate into more stable pricing and better contracts. In global coffee markets, price volatility is high (weather in Brazil/Vietnam affects supply), so Karnataka exporters should hedge/forward contract/negotiate long-term deals with buyers. The world is increasingly buying via digital channels; promoting Karnataka coffee via online marketing, e-commerce, social media, traceability apps, and origin stories helps. Use CBI's “India Coffee App” and other digital tools to register, map plantations, and get certification. Participate in international trade fairs and buyer-seller meets under CBI's export-promotion umbrella. Encourage micro-lots and subscription models (e.g., roasters overseas sourcing “Karnataka origin” directly) to tap niche markets with better pricing. Encourage soil health & biological fertilizers: Use of biological fertilizers and organic matter (compost, green manure) improves soil fertility, reduces the cost of synthetic fertilizers, and can reduce long-term maintenance burdens. Utilize

institutional subsidies for infrastructure: The Coffee Board of India provides support for water augmentation, mechanization, replanting, and infrastructure. Adopt smart irrigation & fertigation systems: Especially helpful in hilly zones of Karnataka. For example, drip irrigation and automation were introduced via Israeli firms to manage water scarcity, helping reduce maintenance cost and risk from erratic rainfall. Use rainwater harvesting and hillside erosion control: Since many coffee plantations lie in the Western Ghats region, managing runoff, conserving soil moisture, and preventing erosion during heavy monsoon contribute to lower maintenance and greater sustainability. Promote climate-resilient varieties and shade-grown systems: Some varieties (especially robusta) are more tolerant of variability, and shade systems buffer extreme rainfall or drought stress. Provide targeted advisories & alerts for monsoon staging: Via digital services such as the Coffee Krishi Taranga (CKT) IVR/advisory system, timely alerts of rainfall and pest/disease risk associated with monsoon can help growers preempt maintenance burdens. Support formation/strengthening of FPOs (Farmer Producer Organizations)/cooperatives: This allows small growers to access inputs, training, infrastructure, and markets more effectively, increasing incomes and stabilizing livelihoods. For example, smallholder farmers in Karnataka saw higher revenue through technology & institution partnerships. Provide stable employment/training for plantation workers: Integrate training programs for workers (pruning, harvesting, quality sorting, post-harvest handling) to improve efficiency, reduce wastage, and improve quality, which benefits both growers & workers. Promote value-added activities at the plantation level: Encourage small growers/plantations to engage in on-site processing (wet milling, drying, packaging) or local micro roasting so that income doesn't rely only on raw green beans. This increases margin per worker and improves employment. Implement social safeguards and labor welfare: Since labor is a key cost and risk, providing fair wages, housing/seasonal work support, and mechanization where appropriate will improve livelihoods and reduce maintenance costs (by lowering labour turnover, absenteeism, and labor wastage). While many plantations are hilly, flatter parts adopt mechanized pulping, drying, and packing to reduce labor costs/maintenance overhead. Promote high-quality plantation rejuvenation and pruning cycles: Old plantations require high maintenance; systematic rejuvenation will reduce cost, increase yield/quality, and lower ongoing maintenance. Training via Coffee Board extension services is available. Introduce sustainable & organic cultivation methods. Quality improvement and better export value: By applying the above (tech adoption, maintenance reduction, climate resilience), plantations will produce higher quality coffee beans, which fetch higher prices in export markets, cushioning livelihood and maintenance cost pressures. Linking small growers directly to export/trading value chains: Via cooperatives/FPOs plus digital platforms, small growers can bypass intermediaries, reduce cost leakage, and benefit from export premiums (specialty/traceability). Use institutional support (Coffee Board) to fund adoption of technology/training for small growers: Include specific schemes targeting small growers/plantation workers for technology upgrades, climate resilience, and mentorship for value-added processing. Promote certification/sustainability credentials: As export markets increasingly

demand sustainability (e.g., deforestation-free supply chains), small growers should be supported to adopt traceability & sustainability certifications that may cost upfront but reduce risk and improve export access.

10. DIRECTIONS FOR THE FUTURE RESEARCH

A similar study can also be conducted in the future for comparing factors responsible for productivity differences in two or more coffee-growing regions or states of India. Besides, other factors like the impact of agronomic factors (fertilizers, irrigation, pruning, weeding) on the productivity of coffee can be studied. The major focus in the study has been given to the export of coffee. Hence, there is scope for further studies focusing on the impact of institutional support on the export of coffee. A more extensive geographical investigation across different coffee-growing areas would also help to confirm the results and investigate their more general relevance. Future research can be conducted based on climate change and its impact on coffee yield and quality in Karnataka. It is directed to carry out the comparative studies between Karnataka and other coffee-producing regions (Kerala, Tamil Nadu, or even international regions like Brazil, Ethiopia, or Vietnam). There is scope for future research to study value chain analysis and sustainability of coffee production. It also directed to conduct future research on the role of government policies and trade agreements in agricultural exports. Understanding factors that affect exports can help in global market positioning. Explore the strategies for starting a coffee export business or specialty coffee brand, leveraging insights on market trends and quality factors. Case studies on Karnataka's coffee industry for use in academic curricula can be generated.

11. CONCLUSION

Coffee producing industry has high growth potential, and abundant untapped opportunities. Since coffee will never cease to be a constant in our daily lives, innovation and competition will remain the leading drivers for this sector. India needs to emerge as a dominant player within the coffee marketplace through its plethora of niche, high-quality offerings. Beyond this, value addition at all stages of coffee processing should be a key area of focus for players within the coffee supply chain in India. While being wary of the ongoing competition from African coffee, Indian coffee exporters should shift some focus from saturated markets to venturing into upcoming markets like Saudi Arabia. For this, the Coffee Board and the Government of India could aid the sector with exploratory budgets to identify new demands and geographies. Italy, Germany, Russian Federation, Belgium, Spain, U.S.A., Jordan, Slovenia, Greece, Switzerland, Finland, Croatia, France, Egypt, Ukraine, Portugal, Israel, Australia, Malaysia and Singapore have been the top twenty countries of Indian coffee exports in the past. Coffee mainly exports oriented commodity. India is the growing exporter of coffee among world competitors. The area, production, and export quantity of coffee registered a similar and fluctuation growth rate during the overall study period. It's indicating that there is scope for increasing the coffee area and production for

strengthening the coffee exports in India. This should be done by adopting new technology and cultivation practices for coffee growing region. There is a fluctuation in export performance of coffee due to the increasing the global exporters but it is stable and positive trend in the overall study period. If government takes proper initiative in supporting the coffee producers and as well as exporters the market will find stable and prospect. It was concluded as there would be steady increasing trend of exports in future. This study on forecasting the coffee exports from India would help the coffee exporters and policymakers to make appropriate decisions.

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